

Perimenopausal Syndrome (PMS): A Case study

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ABSTRACT

Menopausal symptoms are highly prevalent; almost 90% of women seeks advice to cope up. The classical symptoms of menopause are Hot flashes, Anxiety Puffiness on face and lower limbs, Mood swings and Depression. These are experienced by most of women moderate to severe. Vaginal dryness and dyspareunia also become more likely, affecting about 1/3 of the population. The Clinical approach of Hormone therapy and Therapeutic strategies like non hormonal and behavioural changes can also be deployed. Perimenopause begin with irregular menses ends with complete Amenorrhea. There is scenario of irregular cycles with above symptoms from menopausal transition till cessation. Purpose of this review is to integrate the research findings with the clinical presentations of symptomatic peri menopausal women, followed by briefing of treatment given with other likely options.

Keywords: Perimenopausal syndrome, Menopause, Hormones, Rasayan, Panchakarma, Yoga.

INTRODUCTION

Perimenopause is a phase of transition. Many time it starts from age of 35 to 38 and lasts till 49 to 50 years of age. It is typically associated with an increase of the menopausal symptoms like Hot flashes with sudden sweating, Anxiety, Depression related poor sleep, Mood swings, and Vaginal dryness. Erratic oestrogen secretory pattern is in association with the transition. (1)Hormone changes associated with altering menstrual patterns can be seen, high or low oestrogen or no Progesterone responsible for continued and profuse bleeding. This can be continued by per vaginal spotting. Hampered quality of life, disturbed sexual function, lowered bone density, and disturbed reproductive

hormones resulting in irregular menstrual cycles before the onset of the menopausal transition. All these are discussed under this condition.

SWAN, the Study of Women's Health Across the Nation, review seen.(2)

IMPACT:

- Loss of ovarian reserve,

- Inability of granulosa cells to respond to follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) signal with oestradiol production.
- Elevated FSH, reflection of a dwindling follicle pool,
- Diminishing ovarian follicles
- Antimullerian hormone (AMH) leading to the well-characterized monotropic rise in FSH that is a cardinal feature of the menopausal transition and inhibin B. (3)
- Follicles grow more quickly but ovulate at a smaller size (4)
- Increase in luteal phase causes ovulations with minimal follicular phase length, menstrual irregularity deviates hormone pattern (5)
- Low or high oestrogen with anovulatory cycles, longstanding amenorrhea results in menopausal symptoms.

PREVALANCE AND EFFECT :

- Perimenopause affects women in their 40s and 50s, and can significantly impair their physical and mental health.
- Prevalence rate of postmenopausal syndrome is 78% to 90 % according vto various studies of population, but Only 19.5% of the symptomatic women take treatment.

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- Women of high body–mass index (BMI) report worse hot flashes (6)
- Fatigue
- Feelings of worthlessness or excessive guilt
- Decreased ability to think or concentrate.
- Altered cognition with poor sleep quality.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGICAL CHANGES

Specific hormonal events linked to above symptoms . Showing

i)» irregularity of cycles with normal to variable FHS and lower ovarian reserve at early stage

ii)» Variable menstruation with Variable FHS

iii)» late cycles with low FHS

iiii)» Ceased menses low FHS with diminished ovarian reserve.

Elevated FSH is predictive of persistent hot flashes experience.20% in late 50s, 10% in 60s, and 5% in 70.(7)

Heart rate variability associate with increased cardiovascular disease risk.(8)

Depression, Anxiety, and Psychosomatic disorders. (9)

Aims :

1.To Control the menstrual bleeding (Rakt stambhan)

2. Relief from pms symptoms.

Objectives:

1. Replenish dhatu
2. improve general condition, with integrated approach.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

CASE STUDY AND AYURVEDIC APPROACH OF TREATMENT

Study design : single case report

Study setting .. institutional hospital OPD

Blinding ... No

Duration of Study 3 months, followed up every other and 6 mont after Prophylactic treatment started.

A patients came to our OPD facing Hot flashes in the last 4 years with Mild pedal edema on off , gradual weight gain, profuse bleeding during menses since one year . She has Metrorrhagia followed by pv spotting since 3 cycles .

This time she has continued bleeding for 15 days said 3xl sanitary napkins used . So came to us for further evaluation .

Past history : NA , single child of late pregnancy delivered by LSCS.

Presenting symptoms: Heavy bleeding in menses continued with pv spotting Hot flashes bouts of sweat frequently Day night .

Menstrual changes: Regular periods with heavy bleeding, continued by pv spotting.

Vasomotor symptoms: Hot flashes and night sweats.

Sleep disturbance due to sweating , frequent awakenings.

Mood changes: Anxiety, irritability, mood swings.

Other symptoms: Vaginal dryness, frequent urination.

Thorough check up (PS/PV) done.

Uterus was slightly enlarged with regular contour.

Cervix and fornices clear no pain or tenderness was there.

Investigation:

CBC, HB, Hb1Ac, THYROID PROFILE, LIPID PROFILE URINE ME .

TRANSVAGINAL USG done. After these reports to evaluate intra uterine physiology. HYSTEROSCOPY

also done It was showing moth appearance of endometrium with thickness of 17 mm .

D & C done . Sample sent to histopathology fortunately report was normal. Ayurvedic Treatment planned according to pitta prakop and vat vikruti .

Treatment:

AYURVDIC DRUG INTERVENTION:

	Medicines	Dose	Kal	Anupan	Duration
1	Dadimavleh	3gm	Morning		3 month
2	Shatavari ashwagandha churn	3gm each	Morning after dadimavleh	Boiled in milk	3 month
3	Lodhra Nagkeshar churn	3gm each	Twice after meals	Tandulodak	3 month
4	Praval panchamrut	250mg	Twice after meals	Water	3 month
5	Bael candy	3gm	Twice after meals	Roasted Flax seeds and Fennel seeds	3 month
6	Syp. M2 tone and chandanasav	20ml	Twice after meals	Water	3 month
7	Chandanbala lakshadi tail yonipichu	once	At night for 7 days after menses	NA	3 month
8	Shankhpushi tail Nasya	once	At Night	NA	3 month
9	Chandan bala lakshadi matrabasti	once	After menses 7 days	NA	3 month
10	Yoga and Meditation	Omkar, Pranayam, Vajrasan, Virbhadrasan, Viparitkarani, Suptbadhakonasan, Marjrasan, Shavasan, with soothing music of flute.			

RESULT:

Parameters changed after treatment	Before treatment	After treatment
Cholesterol	221 mg/dl [Borderline high]	215mg/dl
Triglycerides	334 mg/dl [High]	252mg/dl
VLDL	66.80mg/dl	50.40 mg/dl
LDL	129.9 mg/dl	110mg/dl
Endometrial thickness	17 mm	7mm after first cycle and scanty after 6 month in TVS
Sanitary Napkins for Menstrual bleeding	3xl : six in a day	XI : four a day after first cycle and onwards
Hot flashes	8-10 times	4-6 times in a day after first cycle and twice onwards
Night sweat	Thrice in night	Once after the first cycle and on off after 3 months

Reports:

DISCUSSION

As prevalence is 78 % and only 19 .5 % receive treatment (13).The treatment suggested for this patient was according to the health measures suggested in Ayurvediya holistic approach.

- Dadimavleh as pachak, pittashamak, agnideepan.
- Lodhra nagkeshar bilva act as rakt stambhan and prasadan rasayan dravya,
- Praval panchamrut, shatavari ashwagandha, guduchi etc. all rasayan drugs helped to replenish the Ras raktadi dhatu.

All the rasayan dravya added to rejuvenate and wellbeing of body.

- Panchakarma like Matrabasti and Nasya chikitsa has its effect of rasayan and balvardhan karma on patient. Nasya has its effect on nervous system. Depression & Anxiety can be calmed with this.
- Balanced diet, yoga, pranayama, meditation was added for the mental and physical health of patient. Thus, with a multi-dimensional treatment of Ayurveda got good results.

CONCLUSION

The basic concept of Ayurveda is “Swasthsya Swastya Rakshanam and Aturasya Vikara Prasamanam” prevention is better than cure.

Menopausal women have disturbed Vata Dosha. Dhatukshay is responsible for Vata Vruddhi it affects various systems in women’s body. From the above

theory we can conclude that various Ayurvedic principles of Rasayana, Vata Shaman and Kapha Vardhan along with Panchakarma, Sadvrata, balanced diet, Yoga, meditation can be helpful for the management of menopausal syndrome.

SUMMARY

The menopausal transition is a challenging period of life for many. Women who are in their career often face this situation, have responsibility of both children and parents. They and society can ill afford to lose any of their human potential. It is therefore critical to continue the efforts outlined here in to understand how perimenopause fits into the context of woman's life and to anticipate and address the symptoms which may cause morbidity or loss of quality of life. Life runs on principles; Ayurveda is science of life with principles. With its insights, Lifestyle changes and proper guidance of treatment can be helpful to overcome such life hampering situation, propagates a happy and healthy womanhood.

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